

Engagement Estimation in Child-Robot Interaction via Transfer Learning from a Pre-trained Facial Emotion Recognition Model

Gonzalo A. García^{1,2}[0000-0003-0022-3717], Rohan Laycock³[0009-0004-7321-3127], Guillermo Pérez¹[0000-0002-8358-996X], J. Gabriel Amores³[0000-0002-3064-3061], Gloria Álvarez³[0000-0001-5840-177X], Manuel Castro¹[0000-0002-6680-4840], and Randy Gomez⁴[0000-0002-3191-6818]

- ¹ *4i Intelligent Insights*, 41092 Seville, Spain {g.garcia,g.perez,m.castro}@4i.ai
² Universidad Internacional de La Rioja (UNIR), 26006 Logroño, La Rioja
³ Universidad de Sevilla, 41004 Seville, Spain {rlaycock,jgabriel,galvarez}@us.es
⁴ Honda Research Institute, 8-1 Honcho, Wako, Japan r.gomez@jp.honda-ri.com

Abstract. *Haru4Kids* is a system developed to emulate the family-oriented robot Haru, enabling child-robot interaction (CRI) within home environments. During a two-week trial with six families, we collected interaction data, including images, which were later labelled by human annotators into four engagement levels. In this study, we present an artificial intelligence model that estimates a child’s engagement level during CRI using pictures captured at one frame per second. Our model leverages *transfer learning*, starting with a pre-trained *ResNet50*-based Facial Emotion Recognition (FER) model, which initially achieved an F1 score of 0.28. Incorporating a *Support Vector Classifier* raised this to 0.48. Further fine-tuning the FER model yielded minimal gains, but applying *Low-Rank Adaptation* (LoRA) significantly improved performance, achieving an accuracy of 0.76, an F1 score of 0.69 in cross-validation and 0.56 in the much stricter validation *leave-one-group-out*. These results highlight the effectiveness of adapting pre-trained emotion models for engagement estimation in CRI. The ultimate goal of this work is to equip robots with some degree of *artificial empathy* —defined here as the ability to sense and adapt to user affective and attentional states— to support more effective and natural interactions. While desirable for any human-interacting robot, this capability is especially critical —yet often absent- in social robots designed for children, a particularly under-explored user group in human-robot interaction research.

Keywords: Child-robot interaction in the wild · Engagement estimation · Affective computing · Emotion recognition · Deep learning · Transfer learning · Low-Rank Adaptation (LoRA)

1 Introduction

Recent research in child-robot interaction (CRI) focuses on how to keep children engaged during interactions with social robots [28]. In this realm, engagement is

typically defined as the level of cognitive, temporal, affective, and behavioural investment in a digital system [35]. Our aim is to estimate engagement during CRI, which poses several challenges—especially in long-term experiments, as children’s interest tends to diminish over time due to the *novelty effect* [30]. While self-report tools like the User Engagement Scale have been widely used [36], automatic engagement estimation techniques are gaining traction, especially in online education and autism studies [49,24,4]. Those methods range from processing physiological signals (e.g., EEG, ECG) to less intrusive techniques like thermal imaging [37,11]. However, such approaches are often impractical in real-world home environments with children. In contrast, video-based engagement estimation is more viable and typically analyses features such as eye gaze, head pose, and facial expressions, often using machine learning models [41,2,50]. Moreover, engagement detection is critical not only to maintain attention during interaction but also to adapt robot behaviour for diverse goals, such as scaffolding learning [19], supporting therapeutic interventions [6,47], or monitoring user well-being [40]. While robots should strive to remain inherently engaging, the capability to detect disengagement enables proactive adaptation, enhances user experience, and informs future design improvements.

In our previous work [14], we introduced the *Haru4Kids* (H4K) platform, designed for use by children in homes. In a two-week cohabitation experiment, the platform displayed an avatar of the robot *Haru* [16,44] on an iPad, mounted on a rotating stand that uses face-tracking to follow the child’s movements. That research was approved by Indiana University’s Institutional Review Board #14363 for human subjects research. H4K collected various types of data during its interactions with children, including images [14,39]. From this, we curated a dataset labelled by humans coding children engagement level from 1 to 4 (low to high). Another vision-based engagement estimation method was used, this one automatic, based on the angle of the user’s face relative to the iPad. The correlation between both methods reached 0.43, highlighting the reliability of visual-based approaches over self-reported metrics [9,37]. However, the annotation process was time-intensive and raised privacy concerns, particularly given the sensitive nature of recording children in home environments.

In our work, engagement is primarily associated with behavioural and emotional signals, following definitions from educational psychology [13,5]. Various approaches have been proposed for automatic engagement recognition using different input signals [26]. Among these, RGB video-based methods are the most common due to their low cost and non-intrusive nature [49]. Moreover, *Convolutional Neural Networks* (CNNs) are a widely used data-driven approach in computer vision, capable of extracting high-level representations from raw image data [29]. However, applying CNNs to engagement recognition—particularly in child-robot interaction—remains challenging due to the limited availability of large, annotated datasets, especially in natural, in-home environments [26].

In this paper, we propose an automatic engagement recognition method for children based on CNNs applied to the face region. To address the training data shortage, we adopt a transfer learning strategy using a pre-trained facial emotion

recognition model. We evaluate our system on our home-collected dataset. While some prior work has applied transfer learning to engagement detection [3,32], to the best of our knowledge this is the first application of *Low-Rank Adaptation* (LoRA) as a fine-tuning method for this problem—well-suited to the limited and imbalanced engagement data typical in CRI, as will be detailed later.

2 Related Work

State of the art: Karimah *et al.* [26] reviewed engagement estimation research from 2010 to 2020, highlighting a shift from traditional machine learning with handcrafted features—such as facial landmarks or action units, gaze, head pose, and body orientation—to deep learning approaches using raw visual inputs. Toolkits like OpenFace, CERT, and *Microsoft Kinect* were commonly used for feature extraction. Modalities ranged from facial images and video to audio, text, physiological signals, and their combinations (fusion). Here, we focus on the literature on facial image-based approaches most relevant to our work. Whitehill *et al.* [49] conducted an early study on binary engagement classification using facial expressions. They compared SVMs with Gabor features (2AFC = 0.86), boosted box filters (0.87), and logistic regression with CERT features (0.93), showing strong performance from handcrafted facial features. They also analyzed inter-rater agreement, compared human and machine judgment cues, and found both to correlate similarly with learning outcomes.

Many recent models have been evaluated on DAiSEE [20], a publicly available dataset with 9,068 video clips of 122 Asian university students (ages 18–30), recorded across six settings. It includes labels of engagement levels (0-3). As deep learning gained traction, Murshed *et al.* [34] evaluated several CNN architectures trained on face images from the DAiSEE dataset (reduced to 3 classes). Their proposed hybrid CNN achieved 0.923 accuracy, outperforming All-CNN (0.76), NiN-CNN (0.832), and VD-CNN (0.865). Santoni *et al.* [46] used OpenFace features to train a bagging ensemble of 1D CNN, 1D ResNet, and hybrid models with SVD-based dimensionality reduction. Tested on the 4-class DAiSEE dataset, their best model reached 0.933 F1 and 0.943 accuracy—amongst the highest reported—demonstrating the effectiveness of deep learning applied to pre-extracted features and ensembling.

Several works adopt transfer learning to address training data scarcity. Ahamad *et al.* [3] benchmarked ten pretrained CNNs (e.g., ResNet18, VGG16) on DAiSEE, with ResNet18 yielding the best performance (0.891 accuracy, 0.888 F1) on 4-class classification. Hu [23] fine-tuned ShuffleNet on a proprietary binary engagement dataset, achieving 0.898 accuracy and 0.883 F1. Moreover, to capture temporal cues, Liao *et al.* [32] combined SE-ResNet-50 (pretrained on VGGFace2) with LSTM and attention modules. Their model achieved 0.588 accuracy and 0.0422 MSE on DAiSEE, and 0.0736 MSE on EmotiW-EP. Similarly, Abedi and Khan [1] proposed a ResNet+TCN hybrid, reaching 0.639 accuracy on DAiSEE (4-class), outperforming prior LSTM- and 3D CNN-based models.

Finally, Yun *et al.* [50] addressed engagement estimation in child-robot in-

teraction using a proprietary 4-level dataset of children’s faces. They use a pretrained CNNs (VGG Face) with LSTM for temporal modeling. Their best model achieved 0.814 accuracy and 0.754 F1, showing the effectiveness of spatial-temporal modeling in settings similar to ours.

Challenges in Engagement Estimation: Several recurring challenges in automatic engagement estimation have been identified in recent surveys [26,43]:

- **Lack of standardized annotation strategies:** Unlike emotion recognition, there is no standard annotation scheme for engagement. Studies vary in whether they label it as discrete, continuous, or a dynamic process, depending on context and goals [43].
- **Subjectivity in external annotation:** Human annotation is inherently subjective and can result in low inter-rater agreement due to the difficulty of consistently interpreting engagement from observable cues [43].
- **Lack of public datasets:** Few large-scale, publicly available datasets exist, making it difficult to train robust deep learning models. The lack of standardized annotations further limits generalization across studies [26].
- **Class imbalance:** Engagement datasets are often skewed toward high engagement, as low-engagement states are less likely to be captured during interaction [26]. To address this, [10] recommend using evaluation metrics robust to imbalance. Macro-F1, in particular, has been shown to provide the most reliable generalization, particularly averaged across folds in k-fold cross-validation, as it is unbiased toward class distribution [12]. Nonetheless, many engagement studies continue to report accuracy as figure of merit, which can be misleading when dominant classes are overrepresented.
- **Temporal modeling and granularity:** Engagement is dynamic, yet many methods rely on static frames. It remains unclear what temporal window (frame- vs. clip-level) best captures engagement signals, making time-series modelling an ongoing challenge [26,43].

3 Methods

3.1 Dataset

Our dataset comprises 19,106 images of children interacting with H4K, captured at 1 FPS during a two-week in-home trial involving six families. H4K engaged with 14 children ($n_{\text{male}} = 9$), aged 6–13 years ($\mu_{\text{age}} = 9.6$). Each image was labelled with an Engagement Level Metric (ELM) from 1 to 4 by five human annotators, where 1 indicates high disengagement, 2 low disengagement, 3 low engagement, and 4 high engagement (for further details about the annotation process, see [14]). To address annotation variability, and to examine its impact on model training, we created three subsets based on *annotator agreement*: ELM3 includes images where at least three annotators agreed (13,539 pictures; a 71% of the total), ELM4 where at least four agreed (5,756; 30%), and ELM5 where all five agreed (1,654; 9%). ELM3 served as our primary dataset given its larger size

and the lowest class imbalance amongst all subsets. For completeness we also consider ELM_{ALL} (16,436; 86%), which corresponds to the full dataset after removing images where no face was detected. All subsets remain imbalanced, with higher engagement levels (3 and 4) being more frequent. Figure 1 shows the distribution of engagement labels (ELMs: 1–4) across the dataset subsets (ELM_{ALL} ; ELM_3 to ELM_5). Figure 2 shows their distribution per family.

We applied RetinaFace [8], a deep learning model for face detection, with a 90% confidence threshold for face detection. Images without a face detected were discarded. The remaining images were cropped to the face region and resized to 224x224 pixels (RGB).

3.2 Validation Strategies

- **Cross-validation (CV):** We performed 80/20 train-validation splits by randomly shuffling data across all families. This tests generalization across unseen images but not necessarily unseen children. All trainable models were evaluated under this scheme.
- **Leave-One-Group-Out (LOGO):** Each fold excludes one family and uses it entirely for validation. This setup better reflects generalization to new users as it is a stricter validation setup, and was only applied to the best-performing model. The median train/validation split across LOGO folds is approximately 71/29, as shown in Table 2. Family 6 was excluded due to its disproportionate size (46% of ELM_3), which could bias results.

3.3 Transfer Learning Framework

Pre-trained FER Model (EmoAffectNet): We adopt a transfer learning strategy using a pre-trained facial emotion recognition (FER) model to address

Fig. 1. Class distribution by dataset.

Fig. 2. Class distribution per family and dataset.

two key limitations in engagement recognition. First, deep learning models require large and diverse datasets to learn generalizable features; however, engagement datasets—especially those involving children—are often small and lack variability [50]. Using a model pre-trained on large-scale facial datasets allows us to retain low-level visual priors while fine-tuning the network for engagement-specific representations. Second, we focus exclusively on facial images, which offers both methodological and practical advantages compared to full-body views; e.g., less occlusions and chances of overfitting to backgrounds. Facial expressions alone provide rich cues for emotional and attentional states, as prior studies have shown, even in the absence of additional modalities [49,25,50].

In this work, we build on insights from our previous study [15] by employing the *EmoAffectNet* framework developed by Ryumina *et al.* [42]. *EmoAffectNet* is a state-of-the-art FER model that comprises two main components: a *ResNet50*-based backbone (a deep CNN with residual connections [21]) for static image recognition, and an LSTM-based temporal module for video input.

We focus exclusively on its *ResNet50* backbone, which was selected for its demonstrated performance across diverse conditions. In [42], the model was initially trained on *ImageNet* [21] for general feature extraction, then fine-tuned on *VGGFace* [38] for facial representation learning, and subsequently adapted to facial emotion recognition using static datasets such as *FER2013* [18] and *AffectNet* [33]. On *AffectNet*, it achieved 0.664 classification accuracy across eight emotion categories, outperforming existing benchmarks and showing robustness to variations in age, gender, lighting, head pose, and occlusion. As shown in Fig. 3, from each facial image, the model outputs seven class probabilities (Happiness, Sadness, Surprise, Fear, Disgust, Anger, and Neutral) via a softmax layer, and just before this layer, it produces a 512-dimensional feature *embedding* that is assumed to encode high-level emotional information.

Model Configurations: We employ *EmoAffectNet* in two configurations. First, in *CNN-7*, we use the original model without modifying its architecture or weights, extracting either the emotion probabilities or the internal embeddings for downstream classifiers. Second, in *CNN-4*, we replace the emotion classification head with a 4-class engagement head and fine-tune the model end-to-end on our dataset, initialised from the pre-trained weights. Both configurations are illustrated in Fig. 3.

3.4 Baseline Methods (CNN-7)

As a baseline, we used the pre-trained model *EmoAffectNet* without modifying its internal weights (that is, *off-the-shelf*). The input image is passed through the FER model to obtain either emotion probabilities or dense intermediate feature embeddings.

- **CI:** from the most confident predicted emotion, we computed a Concentration Index (CI), then converted to an engagement level by: $CI = DEP \times$

Fig. 3. Block diagram of the EmoAffectNet FER framework. The output classes are $N=7$ for emotions predictions (original FER), and $N=4$ for engagement levels.

EW , where **DEP** is the dominant emotion probability and **EW** is an empirically derived weight for that emotion [48]. The resulting continuous CI score (0–1) was mapped to a discrete 4-class engagement level using fixed thresholds. We evaluated CI on the full dataset, as it does not require a training subset.

- **SVC on emotion probabilities (7-D)**: A Support Vector Classifier (SVC) was trained on the 7-class softmax output produced by the model’s final layer. Unlike the fixed CI formula, which applied a predefined mapping, this data-driven approach aimed to learn a more flexible relationship between emotion distributions and engagement levels.
- **SVC on emotion embeddings (512-D)**: An SVC was trained on the 512-dimensional embedding vector from the model’s penultimate layer. These embeddings represent high-level features learned during emotion classification and may contain latent patterns useful for predicting engagement.

3.5 Fine-tuning (CNN-4)

Label treatment strategies: to address dataset limitations, we explored two labelling strategies: (1) training with and without class-weighted loss to account for class imbalance during training, as unbalanced distributions can cause models to underrepresent or ignore minority classes; and (2) using probabilistic soft labels derived from annotator agreement levels to address label ambiguity. For the latter, we used *TensorFlow*’s `categorical_crossentropy` to compute the loss over the soft label distribution.

Layer Freezing Strategies: We fine-tuned the pre-trained EmoAffectNet model by freezing different numbers of convolutional blocks, as shown in Fig. 4. We tested the following six configurations:

- **Full Freeze (1)**: All convolutional blocks were frozen; only the final classification layers were trained for engagement estimation.
- **Partial Freeze (4)**: One, two, three, or four convolutional blocks were unfrozen in turn to allow training of progressively deeper layers.

Fig. 4. Block diagram of ResNet50, showing its five convolutional blocks (stages) and the final classification layers. *Source:* [7].

- **No Freeze (1):** All layers were unfrozen, allowing the entire model to be retrained on our dataset.

We used a 128 batch size, a learning rate of 10^{-4} , and 30 epochs with the Adam optimizer, following the settings in [42]. We used the `sparse_categorical_crossentropy` loss function for standard training with hard labels.

Low-Rank Adaptation (LoRA): We employed Low-Rank Adaptation (LoRA) [22] to fine-tune the pre-trained EmoAffectNet model for engagement classification. This technique limits overfitting and significantly reduces computational overhead (e.g., with $r = 32$, $\alpha = 32$, results in approximately 2.4M trainable parameters, out of 27M total). In our setup, all convolutional layers within each residual block, as well as the final classification layers, were LoRA-trainable.

In addition, in order to identify the best hyperparameters, we performed a grid search over learning rates, batch sizes, and LoRA (r , α). The best-performing setup used a learning rate of 0.001, $r = 64$ and $\alpha = 256$, with batch sizes from 16 to 128 yielding comparable results. These best performing hyperparameters were then used for the LOGO validation setting. During cross-validation (CV), models were trained for up to 20 epochs, while LOGO training used up to 10 epochs. In both cases, early stopping was applied based on validation accuracy. We applied the same grid search to the probability dataset, training 160 models to account for variability and to ensure fair comparison.

Note that LOGO validation was applied only to the LoRA model, after identifying it as the best performer via cross-validation.

4 Results

This section presents the performance of the proposed methods above for engagement prediction on the **ELM3 dataset**. We report accuracy and macro-F1, emphasizing macro-F1 as our primary evaluation metric due to its robustness against class imbalance, as it is less biased toward dominant classes.

Table 1. The different engagement estimation methods used in this work and their performance in cross-validation metrics accuracy (Acc.) and macro-F1 (F1).

Transfer Type	Strategy Description	Model	Acc.	F1	Description
Feature extraction	FER used as a fixed feature extractor; no trainable layers. Outputs emotion probabilities or embeddings for downstream classifiers.	CNN-7 _{CI}	0.53	0.28	Rule-based mapping from dominant emotion.
		CNN-7 _{SVC-prob}	0.32	0.26	SVC on 7-class emotion probability outputs.
		CNN-7 _{SVC-emb}	0.56	0.45	SVC on 512-dimension internal FER embeddings.
Fine-tuning	Pretrained FER model fine-tuned on a 4-class engagement task; replaced 7-class head with 4-class.	CNN-4 _{Freeze}	0.25	0.31	FER full freeze; only classification layers trained.
		CNN-4 _{LoRA-labels}	0.76	0.69	Lightweight fine-tuning via LoRA modules.
		CNN-4 _{LoRA-probs}	0.68	0.56	Same LoRA setup trained on probability-based inputs.

Performance of All Methods: Table 1 summarizes the overall performance of each method, showing the progressive improvements from simple emotion-to-engagement mappings (CNN-7+CI and CNN-7+SVC-emb) to more sophisticated fine-tuning approaches (CNN-4 Freeze and CNN-4 LoRA). The results reflect both F1 scores and accuracy, demonstrating a clear trend of improvement across methods. The baseline, CNN-7+CI, reached an F1 score of 0.28, while CNN-7+SVC-emb achieved 0.45, indicating that deeper feature-based SVC was more effective than direct emotion mapping. The LoRA approach with hard labels (CNN-4 LoRA-labels) achieved the highest F1 score of 0.69 and an accuracy of 0.76.

Transfer Learning Results with CNN-4 Freeze: Among the six configurations tested, full freezing yielded the best performance, with an F1 score of 0.35. As more blocks were unfrozen—starting with one (0.31), then two (0.26), three (0.22), and four (0.19)—performance steadily declined. Unfreezing the entire network resulted in an F1 score of 0.23.

We also tested the use of probability vectors instead of scalar labels, using a balanced configuration (three blocks unfrozen) that retains pretrained features while allowing enough flexibility to adapt to the engagement task. The results showed minimal difference: macro-F1 was 0.21 with scalar labels and 0.19 with probability vectors, indicating no meaningful improvement.

Transfer Learning Results with CNN-4 LoRA: After identifying CNN-4 LoRA as the best-performing method, we further tested its generalization ability through LOGO validation, in order to assess whether the model was capable of generalizing across different family groups, or it was just overfitting.

Table 2 shows the F1 scores for each LOGO split. As expected, F1 scores were lower than the cross-validation result (0.69), since LOGO excludes each validation family from training. However, keeping in mind that a classifier based solely on sheer chance would have an F1 lower than 0.25 (as classes are highly

Table 2. LOGO validation dataset characteristics and performance across the subsets ELM3, ELM4, and ELM5. The most representative metric is $F1_w$ at ELM3.

Family	Family IDs		# Images		Ratio		ELM3		ELM4		ELM5	
	Train	Val.	Train	Val.	Train	Val.	Acc	$F1_w$	Acc	$F1_w$	Acc	$F1_w$
F01	2,3,4,5,6	1	11,273	2,266	0.83	0.17	0.34	0.37	0.54	0.63	0.83	0.84
F02	1,3,4,5,6	2	11,329	2,210	0.84	0.16	0.37	0.41	0.41	0.51	0.76	0.84
F03	1,2,4,5,6	3	13,254	285	0.98	0.02	0.60	0.56	0.38	0.46	0.93	0.96
F04	1,2,3,5,6	4	11,520	2,019	0.85	0.15	0.46	0.49	0.81	0.84	0.91	0.94
F05	1,2,3,4,6	5	12,989	550	0.96	0.04	0.34	0.29	0.48	0.45	0.75	0.77
F06	1,2,3,4,5	6	7,330	6,209	0.54	0.46	0.52	0.48	0.46	0.44	0.39	0.29
Avg.	–	–	11,283	2,257	0.83	0.17	0.44	0.43	0.52	0.56	0.76	0.77
Median	–	–	11,425	2,115	0.84	0.16	0.41	0.45	0.47	0.49	0.79	0.84

unbalanced), we see that the LOGO results even for ELM3 are not so bad, as half of the groups still reached values around 0.50.

On the other hand, Family F05 had the lowest F1 score at 0.29 –around the value of pure chance–, highlighting variability across different groups. See a more detailed analysis in the *Discussion* section.

5 Discussion

Overview of All Methods: This study aimed to develop a robust, data-efficient method for estimating child engagement in CRI, addressing two major challenges in the field: (1) the lack of large, high-quality engagement datasets, and (2) severe class imbalance. We leveraged a single pre-trained FER model and applied transfer learning to adapt it for engagement classification.

We first evaluated three baseline methods using the FER model without modification: a Concentration Index, an SVC on emotion probabilities, and an SVC on embeddings. While simple emotion mappings performed poorly (macro-F1 0.26–0.28), the deeper embeddings improved performance to 0.45—supporting our hypothesis that pretrained emotion features contain useful visual cues for engagement. Next, we explored progressive fine-tuning by unfreezing convolutional blocks. Surprisingly, the best result (macro-F1 = 0.35) came from the fully frozen model—where only the final classification layers were retrained. Unfreezing additional layers steadily reduced performance, down to 0.19. Validation accuracy remained stable at 0.59, indicating increased overfitting to majority classes.

These results suggest that the pretrained FER features were already well aligned with the task, and that retraining disrupted them –likely due to data scarcity and class imbalance. Given that full freezing outperformed all other configurations, we turned to LoRA, which freezes the original weights and introduces small trainable matrices into selected layers, allowing lightweight, task-specific adaptation without modifying the backbone (as the weights were already well-aligned with the task).

While cross-validation yielded good scores for LoRA, these results likely overestimate generalization, as images from the same child appear in both training

and validation sets. Using a 70/30 split instead of the usual 80/20, produced a drop on those scores, showing sensitivity to training size but not true user-level generalization. To address this, we applied LOGO validation. This highlights that while LoRA improves robustness, generalization to unseen users remains uneven –likely due to limited and not fully consistent engagement data.

5.1 Impact of Annotator Agreement and Label Quality

We assessed the impact of *supposed* annotation quality increase using three subsets with increasing annotator agreement: ELM3 (≥ 3), ELM4 (≥ 4), and ELM5 (5/5). All evaluations used LOGO validation with our best model, CNN-4 LoRA. Each subset was split into training and validation sets—so even under class imbalance, the model could be trained, and having all four classes present in validation remains important compared to classes not appearing at all.

Subset ELM3, while the largest, had the lowest agreement and served as the main training set, as discussed earlier. The results obtained with ELM5, despite having the highest agreement, *must be interpreted with caution*: it was the smallest, most imbalanced, and had limited class diversity—e.g., in ELM5, F03 included only one class, F04 and F05 two, and F01 and F02 lacked one class each, as shown in Figure 2. High F1 scores in ELM5 likely reflect reduced classification complexity rather than true generalization. ELM4 offered the best trade-off: higher agreement than ELM3, broader class coverage than ELM5, and more consistent F1 scores across families, as shown in Table 2. In ELM4, only F03 lacked one class in validation. Based on these results, we hypothesize that *higher annotator agreement improved label quality, which in turn helped the model learn more effectively*—even with fewer samples. The fact that CNN-4 LoRA achieved strong LOGO performance on ELM4—despite the smaller dataset size—supports that idea, as well as previous literature [17]. However, further experiments are needed to confirm this. In any case, more balanced, larger and diverse datasets are essential to fully validate model generalization claims.

5.2 Comparison with Prior Work

Many studies on engagement estimation, particularly using the DAiSEE dataset, report high accuracy –often on simplified tasks (e.g., 2- or 3-class setups) or favourable splits (e.g., same subjects in train and validation). However, accuracy alone can be misleading in imbalanced settings, as it overemphasises dominant classes [10]. Therefore, in this work, in addition to accuracy, we have used macro-F1 and LOGO validation to better capture generalization across all classes and unseen users in-the-wild.

Ahmad *et al.* [3] benchmarked ten pretrained CNNs (e.g., ResNet50, VGG16), using them for classification and as feature extractors for downstream classifiers (e.g., SVC), similar to our approach. Their best model achieved 0.687 F1 on a 3-class task, compared to our CNN-4 LoRA with 0.69 F1 on a 4-class task. Our relative improvement may be due to the use of pre-trained models from emotion

and facial feature datasets, which could enhance the model’s ability to capture engagement-specific features.

Liao *et al.* [32] proposed a CNN-LSTM architecture using SE-ResNet-50 pre-trained on VGGFace2 and FER-2013, resembling our approach, but they added LSTM for temporal modeling, capturing engagement dynamics. Their model achieved 0.588 accuracy (MSE = 0.0422) on DAiSEE, highlighting the challenges of temporal modeling in engagement estimation.

Santoni *et al.* [45,46] used pre-extracted facial features from OpenFace, including 709 values (e.g., AUs), and trained a bagging ensemble of CNNs, ResNet, and hybrid models, achieving 0.933 F1 and 0.943 accuracy on the 4-class DAiSEE dataset (compared to our 0.69 F1 and 0.76 accuracy). Their use of SMOTE addressed class imbalance by generating more data for minority classes. Their impressive performance results from their hybrid approach, combining handcrafted features with deep learning, easing the burden on CNNs and overcoming the limitations of deep learning with limited data. In contrast, we rely on pretrained models to automatically extract facial features from images. Santoni’s method currently holds the highest benchmark on DAiSEE, supporting the reliability of static vision systems focusing on facial features.

Yun *et al.* (2018) [50] were amongst the first to apply deep learning to child engagement estimation, using pretrained models due to limited data. Their system used facial videos with a pre-trained CNN (VGG Face) for feature extraction and LSTM for temporal modelling. Their dataset, consisting of 30 children aged 7 with 6,829 samples, used majority voting among 7 labellers. They initially used a 4-class annotation scheme but later simplified it to a 2-class system (Engaged vs. Disengaged) due to class imbalance, achieving a F1 score of 0.754.

While their approach is similar to ours in using pretrained CNNs, we focus on still images, whereas they used video clips. Their dataset size is comparable to ours, but they simplified the problem to 2 classes, unlike our 4-class approach, which achieved 0.69 F1. Despite differences in methodology, both studies aim to address CRI engagement with similar datasets and feature extraction techniques. Both works demonstrate the effectiveness of pretrained models for facial engagement estimation, overcoming data limitations and class imbalance.

5.3 Limitations and Future Directions

While the results of this study are highly promising, several limitations remain. First, all subsets (ELM3, ELM4, and ELM5) suffer from significant class imbalance. This highlights the need for more balanced and diverse datasets to truly assess generalization. The inherent challenge stems from the natural dynamics of engagement: lower-engagement states often result in early dropout, leading to underrepresentation of these cases in the data collection process.

Furthermore, we chose to extract still images at 1 FPS rather than storing full videos to limit storage requirements, reduce privacy risks associated with continuous recordings, and streamline the annotation process. Nevertheless, temporal information might improve model performance.

Additionally, while this study demonstrates technical feasibility, deploying such systems in real-world child contexts requires careful ethical reflection and adherence to emerging regulations on emotion AI for vulnerable users [27]. Future work should include participatory design with families and ethical experts to evaluate social acceptability and potential risks, as we have already done in our previous work [31].

6 Conclusion

This study validates a data-efficient strategy for engagement detection in child-robot interaction: leveraging pretrained emotion recognition models and applying minimal, targeted fine-tuning via LoRA. Despite limited training data, models like CNN-4 LoRA achieved some generalization to unseen individuals – particularly when trained on well-annotated subsets. This opens the door for more accessible, deployable affective systems in real-world CRI.

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